

Genomic analysis datacenter

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Abstract—With the aim of completing the creation of a regional level genomics and epigenetics laboratory, in addition to the acquisition of sequencers and other laboratory equipment, it was necessary to design and build a Data Center that is capable of processing, analyzing, store and transmit the collected data.

Keywords—Datacenter, genomic, epigenetics, sequencer, HPC, computing

I. INTRODUCTION

As is well known, "Friends Don't Let Friends Build Data Centers" has been around for some years.

In general this is true for most of the practical cases, but there are some exceptions, due, for example, to the type of data processed, the available bandwidth, the latency of the transmission systems, the criticality of the data processed.

The indication of the General Management was to develop an ecosystem capable of processing data from genomic sequencers and other analysis instruments that would interface with it. It consists of a computing, network and storage architecture strongly oriented towards the development of research projects and activities in support of clinical diagnostics, guaranteeing performance in terms of latency between computing and storage nodes and space expansion capacity storage on parallel file systems that are not typically found in PaaS (Platform as a Service), or IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) services.

II. RELATED WORK

The infrastructure to be created aims to be innovative in many respects:

- it must be based on Open-source technology that can be acquired free of charge without the use of licenses as well as executable on entirely Open-source platforms, such as Linux and KVM;
- it is designed open, portable and interoperable towards the solutions of different suppliers (such as Microsoft Azure, Amazon EC2, etc.) thanks to standard interfaces, in order to avoid the so-called risk of vendor lock-in (dependence on a single supplier);

- implements a modular system of infrastructure services (IaaS Infrastructure as a Service) based on the network and configured for specialized components, designed to be expandable towards a model of:
 - offer for consumption ("pay per use") of computing and storage resources
 - provision of intermediate services for the development, installation and implementation of software (middleware or runtime) in Platform as a Service (PaaS) mode;
 - distribution of applications or data in Software as a Service (SaaS) mode;
- must be flexible in terms of architectures and implementation models, prefiguring multiple or mixed scenarios of offer/use of services (public-private-hybrid) and the possibility of multi-tenant use, i.e. virtually separate instances for single organizations, offices, groups of users;
- must adopt safety specifications that ensure:
 - compliance with the requirements imposed by the management of genomics data;
 - compliance with the guidelines for the use of cloud systems in the Public Administration.

The calculation and storage systems, initially intended for the sequenced data analysis project, will subsequently be available for work groups or research also in other fields such as, for example, numerical simulation in the genetic field (docking programs, dynamic molecular, etc...).

The basic architecture of the system to be created is that of a private cloud system that allows the use of HPC resources in a native way (bare-metal). For the realization we intend to acquire the following hardware components:

- computing nodes: resources to be used both in a virtualised/containerised manner and in a "bare metal" architecture;
- service nodes: I/O node, login node, management and monitoring node, etc.;
- management nodes for setting up the cloud infrastructure;
- high performance storage system;
- network infrastructure for overall system management;
- network infrastructure for fast and low latency interconnection of the nodes.

CALCULATION NODES

The computing nodes will have to be based on highly integrated platforms and suitable for optimizing spaces, absorbed and dissipated electrical power.

Acceptable form factors are racks with a dual-processor motherboard in a single rack unit (1U).

It should be noted that the reference unit, for the network ports, is the biprocessor; for each biprocessor there must be 2 25Gb ethernet ports and 1 100Gb InfiniBand port, as specified in the dedicated paragraph. On each server, the 25GbE card must provide support for Switch Independent Partitioning (NPAR) up to 16 partitions and for RoCE, RoCEv2, and iWARP.

The power supply must be redundant in 1+1 mode. The fall of a power supply must not cause any variation in the performance and/or in the computing power generated by the nodes contained in the chassis.

The processors of the computing nodes must be equipped with 2 x86 64bit multi-core processors.

The compute nodes memory must be approved and certified by the motherboard manufacturer and it will not be allowed to mix memory modules of different sizes, types, speeds or manufacturers.

The maximum computational power required by the specific processor refers to the theoretical peak performance (Rpeak). It refers to the double precision value for CPU floating point operations and is calculated theoretically using the following formula:

$$\text{GFLOPS} = \text{N_cores_CPU} * \text{max_turbo_frequency} * \text{floating_point_operations_per_clock_cycle}$$

All nodes shall be equipped with an IPMI version 2.0 or higher and Redfish compliant board management controller (BMC). The BMC must allow encrypted access to the serial console over the network (e.g. SSH), remote management of the power supply, the ability to interact with the system in virtual console mode (e.g. KVM).

The BMC must be equipped with a dedicated network interface at least 1Gbps Base-T.

Must be supported:

- remote management protocols such as: VNC, Java & HTML5 GUI;
- virtual consoles & vMedia;
- automatic BIOS and firmware update scheduling functionality for internal components;
- support of the Redfish protocol (RESTful API);
- Server Configuration and Firmware lock-down;
- digitally signed Firmware update;
- Firmware rollback function;
- protection of firmware updates of internal components;
- secure Default Password;
- secure deletion of all internal server storage devices (ISE);
- Active Directory support and LDAP authentication;
- SNMP v3;

- IP Range Blocking;
- TLS 1.2 communications;

FAT NODES

FAT compute nodes are characterized by a high amount of volatile memory. The minimum characteristics of these nodes are:

- Dual socket with at least 3.0Ghz processor, with at least 18 cores in each socket;
- At least 1.536Gb ECC RAM; the number of memory modules must be the same as the number of communication bus channels in order to make the most of it;
- hot-swap storage system with HW raid controller with RAID0/1 support;
- 2 x 480Gb SSDs;
- 2x25GbE NICs;
- 1x100Gbit/s EDR Infiniband port HBA;
- 1Gbps management port;
- redundant power supply;
- NBD 3-year on-site warranty.

We initially intend to adopt 2 FAT nodes.

The theoretical peak performance of the single node should be 3110 GFLOPS (reference processors Intel Xeon Gold 6154 3.0Ghz, 18C/36T).

THIN NODES

Thin compute nodes have less volatile memory than FAT nodes. The minimum characteristics of these nodes are:

- Dual socket at least 2.6Ghz, at least 12 cores each socket;
- 768 Gb ECC RAM: the number of memory modules must be the same as the number of communication bus channels in order to make the most of it;
- hot swap storage system with HW raid controller with RAID0/1 support;
- 2 x 480Gb SSDs;
- 2x25GbE NICs;
- 1x100Gbit/s EDR Infiniband port HBA;
- 1Gbps management port;
- redundant power supply;
- NBD 3-year on-site warranty.

We initially intend to adopt 10 THIN nodes.

4 The theoretical peak performance of the single node should be 1776 GFLOPS (reference processors Intel Xeon Gold 6126 2.6Ghz, 12C/24T).

MANAGEMENT NODES

The virtualization management nodes will provide an OpenStack environment on which to run multiple services (keystone/dashboard/glance etc..). These central service nodes are configured as follows:

- Dual socket at least 2.2Ghz, at least 10 cores for each socket;
- at least 192 Gb ECC RAM: the number of memory modules must be the same as the number of communication bus channels in order to make the most of it;
- hot swap storage system with HW raid controller with RAID0/1 support;
- 2 x 480Gb SSDs;
- 2x25GbE NICs;
- 1x100Gbit/s EDR Infiniband port HBA;
- 1Gbps management port;
- redundant power supply;
- NBD 3-year on-site warranty.

It is intended to acquire 4 central service nodes.

The reference model for the management node processors is the Intel Xeon Gold 4114 2.6G, 10C/20T.

VIRTUALIZATION NODES

The computing nodes for virtual machines are configured as follows:

- Dual socket at least 2.2Ghz, at least 10 cores for each socket;
- at least 384 Gb ECC RAM: the number of memory modules must be the same as the number of communication bus channels in order to make the most of it;
- hot swap storage system with HW raid controller with RAID0/1 support;
- 2 x 480Gb SSDs;
- 2x25GbE NICs;
- 1x100Gbit/s EDR Infiniband port HBA;
- 1Gbps management port;
- redundant power supply;
- NBD 3-year on-site warranty.

We intend to acquire 4 computational nodes for virtual machines.

The reference model for the virtualization node processors is the Intel Xeon Gold 4114 2.6G, 10C/20T.

NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE

The data center infrastructure will be interconnected via different networks, each with distinct purposes. Compute nodes and storage must be connected via a high-speed, low-latency network such as InfiniBand. The management nodes will be connected to all the other nodes via a dedicated 25Gbps Ethernet network.

The supply must include, for all the networks described above, the relative active and passive devices (switches, patch panels) for interconnection and cabling, as better specified in the following paragraphs.

HIGH SPEED AND LOW LATENCY NETWORK

The InfiniBand (IB) network will connect all the compute, virtualization, management and storage system servers. The delivery must include copper or fiber cabling from the switches to the individual nodes. The length of the cables must be suitably sized to allow direct connection between switches and nodes.

The interconnection must meet the following minimum requirements:

- EDR connection switches or versions;
- all nodes must converge towards the IB edr 100Gbps network and in non-blocking mode;
- point-to-point bandwidth not lower than 100 Gbps;
- internode point-to-point latency not exceeding 1.0 microseconds.

For the creation of this network, the network interfaces, the switching devices and the cables must be respectively of the same manufacturer and certified for mutual use. The solution offered must also include management, management and provisioning software for the interconnection system capable of collecting and displaying in maximum detail both performance data and data relating to the state of health of the system, allowing for equipment tuning and preventive maintenance of the components.

IN-BAND NETWORK

It is the internal connection network (in-band) on which to connect all the computing, virtualization and storage nodes to the management nodes. The requested type is Ethernet with a speed of 25Gbps.

A highly reliable solution must be provided.

For this type of network it is necessary to provide one or more switches with a total number of ports sufficient to connect all the nodes, which implements the management of VLANs and which is able to distribute them automatically, with a specific protocol, towards the edge switches. All the nodes and devices of the electrical systems (panel and PDU), air conditioning and UP must be connected to this network; these network ports must be connected to a pair of out-of-band Gigabit switches as they do not require performance.

A redundant connection to the access switches must be provided, with LACP protocol or equivalent. The access switches must allow maintenance and software/firmware updating operations to be carried out without service interruption. The supply must include Cat6 type cabling.

It is expected that:

- a pair of high-performance switches with densities of up to 72 ports at 25Gbps line rate full duplex (3.6 Tbps switching fabric capacity) are provided;
- ONIE support is guaranteed for the use of alternative linux-based operating systems;
- support for network operating systems other than those developed by the equipment manufacturer is guaranteed;
- the use of different Operating Systems cannot affect the HW support of the devices;

- support for Priority-based flow control (PFC), data center bridge exchange (DCBX) and enhanced transmission selection (ETS) is guaranteed;
- power supplies and fans are redundant and hot swappable; moreover, there must be no further SPOF (Single Point of Failure);
- the interconnection between the aforementioned devices must take place via multi chassis lag technologies in order to obtain a highly reliable solution.

OUT-OF-BAND NETWORK

It is the network dedicated to the system management of the computing cluster; in order to interconnect all the nodes of the HPC system to the management network, the supply of all the necessary hardware and software components is required for the creation of an Ethernet-type network with a speed of at least 1Gbps.

The out-of-band fabric will have to be implemented via a 48-port line rate Gbps Ethernet switch with a 10Gbps sfp+ uplink and which can be grouped with stacking technologies.

STORAGE ARCHITECTURE

The computing system must be equipped with a dedicated storage system. The intention is to structure the storage on 3 levels, with different speeds and capacities (multi-tier infrastructure).

The goal is to get an architecture that provides broad compatibility and support with today's standards for accessing parallel file systems, such as the Ceph file system.

The characteristics common to level I and level II storage must be:

- absence of single point-of-failure through redundancy of all critical components, in particular each node/head must have at least two controllers or logical units;
- adoption of technologies that ensure high reliability such as block-level data replication;
- the connection of the I and II level storage to the computing nodes will take place via the InfiniBand network;
- the connection must be redundant on 25Gbps ethernet fabric;
- the storage system must allow the creation of isolated "tenants" within a pool of common resources;
- the storage system must support the possibility of evolving in "scale out" or by adding new nodes and increasing the amount of space in a transparent manner and without impact on operations;
- certified compatibility with the cluster parallel file system solution that will be proposed;
- exposure of the storage service using NFS and CIFS protocols with full support for Access Control Lists ("NT-style" ACLs);
- support for defining usage quotas;
- support of the "Snapshot" function that can be activated at any time;

- possibility of hot swapping (hot swap) all critical hardware components (power supply units, controllers, disks, etc.);
- all supplied devices, including hard-disks, must be certified as Enterprise class;
- it must be possible to update the firmware without service interruption;
- the storage devices must have functions able to guarantee the absolute consistency of the data in the event of a fault such as, for example, the "de-staging" of the data present in the cache before switching off in the event of a power failure;
- scale-out devices must have self-diagnosis capabilities or be interconnected to a fault detection system, in order to promptly inform system administrators of any faults;
- the storage devices must have monitoring functions in terms of system use and performance or be interconnected to an external monitoring system.

I LEVEL STORAGE

Level I storage will be used for analyzing the data processed on the fat and thin nodes.

The minimum size is at least 200Tb in flash technology, aggregate performance of I/O on the file system equal to at least 20 GByte/sec.

II LEVEL STORAGE

Secondary tier storage will be used for medium-term data retention and as a storage area for data processed by compute nodes.

The minimum size is at least 700Tb in capacitive technology with minimum performance of at least 2Gbps in reading and writing.

III LEVEL STORAGE

Level III storage will be used for long-term archiving and backup: the initial supply will be at least 700Tb but the proposed solution must provide total expandability of the storage space up to 2PByte without having to add new front-end devices but only by buying records.

Level III storage must be composed of a dual controller architecture with at least 16GB of total cache (in Active - Active mode). This technology must be able to address at least 2 Pbyte Raw for maximum expandability.

Tiering, Replication, Snapshotting, SSD read cache, Thin Provisioning functions must also be supported.

The space provided by this object must be protected with raid technology capable of addressing all mechanics dynamically in double parity (a single raid to address all the required space).

The entire back-end and front-end chain must support at least 12 Gbps SAS connectivity and possibly JBOD drives.

TEST VERIFICATION

Testing is carried out, even during construction, in collaboration with the successful tenderer, by a commission appointed by the Sole Supervisor of the Procedure, whose members are chosen from experts in HPC and plant engineering.

The acceptance procedure for a maximum duration of 30 calendar days starting from the date of signing the "Delivery Report", will be carried out by the technical staff assisted by the Supplier's staff. The final testing of the functionality and performance of the infrastructure will consist in the execution of the procedures which are defined below.

CALCULATION NODE VALIDATION PROCEDURES

1. Execution of the Infiniband network performance tests (Perftest): in order to verify the correct functioning of the fast interconnection network between Infiniband nodes and the related bandwidth and latency, the `ib_write_bw`, `ib_write_lat`, `ib_read_bw`, `ib_read_lat` provided with the "Perftest" suite. These tests, which will involve pairs of nodes, must be carried out in such a way as to verify the performance of all the nodes that make up the system. The tests must be performed under the following conditions:
 - a. each test must be performed individually and not in competition with other tests;
 - b. the test between two separate nodes must be performed in bidirectional mode (with the "-b" option);
 - c. each test must be performed for a duration of no less than 20 seconds.

Acceptance value for this test:

All tests will pass if the obtained bandwidth and latency values are equal at least 85% of the values declared by the manufacturer.

2. Running the HPL (High Performance Linpack) benchmark: in order to verify the correct functioning of the nodes dedicated to parallel computing and verify the aggregate computing performance, two separate runs of the benchmark must be performed under the following conditions:
 - a. all the calculation nodes (thin + fat) of the system must be involved and the Infiniband interconnection network must be used;
 - b. the runs must have a duration of at least 10 hours.

Acceptance value for this test:

The test will be passed if both runs reach at least 60% of the computational capacity aggregate peak (theoretical peak performance) offered.

3. Execution of the STREAM benchmark: in order to verify the correct functioning of the memory RAM and its bandwidth, the STREAM benchmark should be run on all nodes of the system (both thin/fat computing nodes and service nodes).

Acceptance value for this test:

the achievement of at least 80% of the memory bandwidth declared in the technical specifications of the manufacturers of the supplied hardware.

STORAGE SYSTEM VALIDATION PROCEDURES

In order to verify the correct operation of the multi-tier storage system and the relative I/O performance, all the tests described below must be performed:

Execution of the IOR benchmark: the objective of this test is to measure and verify the aggregate performance of I/O on the file system mounted by the compute nodes on fast storage. For these tests the IOR benchmark (<https://github.com/hpc/ior>) must be used. The tests must be performed under the following conditions:

1. the Infiniband interconnection network must be used;
2. the POSIX data access interface shall be used;
3. the dimensions of the block size and of the aggregate file size must be such as to minimize the effect of the cache and balance the workload;
4. before each test, the operations of clearing the cache and remounting the file system must be performed on all nodes.

Running the mdtest benchmark: the objective is to verify the quality of the metadata management system associated with the installed FS. For these tests the IOR benchmark (<https://github.com/hpc/ior>) must be used. The tests must be performed under the following conditions:

1. the Infiniband interconnection network must be used;
2. the POSIX data access interface shall be used;

INSTALLATIONS

The supply of a perfectly functional Data Center is required in the solution of a single or modular container system, which internally includes all the systems functional to the calculation center and in particular it is required that, for each component, the following constraints are respected :

- prefabricated:
 - it must have dimensions not exceeding 9mx5mx3,5m;
 - the panels that make up the walls and ceiling of the prefabricated module must guarantee fire resistance, thermal and acoustic insulation and waterproofing;
 - inside the prefabricated module there must be a thermal containment system aimed at avoiding mixing between the hot air

- produced by the IT cabinets and the cold air emitted by the air conditioning units;
 - the surface treatment must guarantee protection from corrosion suitable for type C3 environments (urban, lightly polluted industrial);
 - it must guarantee EI30 fire resistance according to the EN 13501-2 standard;
 - a logo will have to be made on the external wall;
- UPS system;
 - Modular static UPS;
 - the UPS must house swappable power modules in order to guarantee internal redundancy of the N+1 type.
 - the batteries must be sized to guarantee an autonomy of at least 10 minutes with the load absorbed by the hardware envisaged by these specifications;
 - hot swappable modular batteries;
 - unique static swappable bypass;
 - intelligent redundant and swappable power modules;
 - certified efficiency of at least 95% starting from 20% of the load;
 - power modules equipped with field replaceable fans;
 - communication card that allows access via Web and via SNMP protocol;
- conditioning solution:
 - direct expansion conditioning systems;
 - system complete with inverter compressor, EC fans, condensate pumps, remote condensers, remote temperature sensors for each installed rack;
 - the system must guarantee N+1 redundancy on the cooling units and the possibility of being programmed at least with the following methods: 1) circular redundancy 2) master/slave;
 - each machine must be equipped with redundant power supply;
- rack systems;
 - the rack cabinets must have an aluminum frame to reduce their specific weight given the density of the components.
 - the cabinets must be fixed to the floor and equipped with leveling devices and provided with connections for earthing;
 - a sufficient number of cabinets must be provided for containing all the hardware covered by these specifications plus a number of 2 empty cabinets for future expansions;
 - the cabinets must be equipped with multi-socket Rack PDUs with management which must be equipped with a display to indicate the aggregate value of the electrical absorption and equipped with temperature sensors;
- electricity distribution;
 - general three-phase panel sized for the calculation infrastructure described above;
 - overhead ducts for power and data cables and optical fibres;
 - busways for power distribution to the rack cabinets;
- each PDU rack must be protected by a circuit breaker dedicated to it;
- all the necessary electrical connections inside the prefabricated module;
- fire extinguishing system composed of;
 - inert gas extinguishing system with cylinders on site;
 - discharge nozzles;
 - detection control unit and extinguishing command;
 - pipes complete with fittings, bends, joints, caps;
- video surveillance system:
 - based on at least two IP cameras, one for indoors and one for outdoors;
 - POE support;
 - resolution at least 2 Mpixel;l
- lighting system
 - ordinary interior lighting;
 - internal emergency lighting;
- central monitoring software that allows you to:
 - make available a single dashboard through which to know, in real time, the state of health of the Data Center and the operating parameters of the monitored devices;
 - use SNMP standard protocols;
 - be accessible via web browser;
 - allow the creation of reporting groups for email notifications;
 - make an event log available;

III CONCLUSION

The above represents the project and the technical specifications for the acquisition and construction of a data center for the management and analysis of data generated by genetic sequencers and the specificity of the scope of application has determined design constraints that have been taken into consideration during all phases of project development. A GPU-based solution is intentionally not adopted as it is considered a data center development to be implemented in a second phase of the project.